

Agro2Circular

D7.3 – Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results

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Authors: Aran Blanco (KVC); Alba Matamoros (KVC)

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Table of contents

List of abbreviations	8
Glossary.....	10
1 Executive summary <abstract>	11
2 Introduction	12
3 Agro2Circular Engagement Process	14
4 Ecosystem Analysis.....	16
4.1 Analysis of the Citizen Engagement Infrastructure [updated]	17
4.1.1 Regional Level.....	17
4.1.2 Local Level	26
4.2 Stakeholders and Services	28
5 Diagnosis	29
5.1 Selection of Existing Infrastructure [updated].....	29
5.2 Preliminary Review.....	30
5.3 Levels of Participation in A2C Activities [updated].....	31
5.4 A2C Virtual and Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]	35
5.4.1 A2C Virtual Infrastructure [updated]	35
5.4.2 A2C Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]	37
6 . Action Plan.....	41
6.1 Regional Workshop on Public Engagement [updated]	41
6.2 Public Engagement Activities [updated]	43
6.2.1 Inform level [updated].....	43
6.2.2 Consult [updated]	53
6.2.3 Involve level [updated].....	55

6.2.4	Collaborate level [updated]	62
6.2.5	Empower [updated]	67
7	Evaluation of the results	69
8	Conclusions	71
9	Bibliography	73

List of Tables

Table 1	Virtual and face-to-face infrastructures	30
Table 2	Regional stakeholder panel	63
Table 3.	EU Stakeholder Panel.	64

List of Figures

Figure 1	Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders	14
Figure 2	Spectrum of Public Participation. Source: <i>Vancouver Mayor's Engaged City Task Force. Final Report.</i> (2014) based on IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation.....	15
Figure 3	Region of Murcia and the municipality of Alhama de Murcia. Source: IDERM	16
Figure 4.	Citizen participatory platform (Region of Murcia)	18
Figure 5.	Screenshot of the SAT linked to the website of CARM ministry of Agriculture ...	19
Figure 6	SIT MURCIA (Geoportal) homepage	21
Figure 7	EIEL CARM showing equipment for urban waste management in Alhama de Murcia.....	21
Figure 8	Screenshot of Plataforma Tierra	22
Figure 9	Training section of Plataforma Tierra	23
Figure 10.	LOOPA website	24
Figure 11.	LOOPARM Best practices indicator framework	24
Figure 12.	A2C as success case at LOOPA dynamic catalogue	25
Figure 13.	Preliminary SWOT matrix: engagement processes for the implantation of the CE	31

Figure 14. Levels of public participation.....	32
Figure 15. A2C website homepage (What? section) in English	35
Figure 16. Event created for the collaboration with Biowaste Club of HOOP project in April 2023.....	36
Figure 17 Zones of the Alhama market with food stalls (marked in light green). One of the areas is located around the food market hall (Mercado de Abastos), marked with a shopping cart on the map.	38
Figure 18 Panel of opportunities for public engagement.....	42
Figure 19 Plenary session	42
Figure 20. Last news published at A2C local website	44
Figure 21. Events published at the local website	44
Figure 22. Agrofood working day in Cartagena.....	45
Figure 23. Agrofood working day in Murcia.....	45
Figure 24. Poster of the webinar.....	46
Figure 25. Workshop on circular business models at CCRI.....	46
Figure 26. CETEC during the workshop at UPCT.....	47
Figure 27. A2C poster at the "Challenges of bioeconomy" conference.....	48
Figure 28. Photos of Cajamar Talent Area Conference	49
Figure 29. Exposition on multilayer films at CETEC/CTNC booth. Murcia Science Week 2022.....	50
Figure 30. Food and nutraceutical compounds at CTNC booth during Science Week 2024	50
Figure 31. Murcia FOOD Brokerage Event 2023	50
Figure 32. CETEC presenting A2C at CONAMA 2024	50
Figure 33. CJM at the Researchers' Night 2024 in Almeria	50
Figure 34. PROEX at FRUITATTRACTION 2024.....	50
Figure 35. Students during an Open Day at CETEC, Green Week 2023	51
Figure 36. Demonstrator 4 at DMC Facilities. Site visit during General Assembly in October 2024.....	52
Figure 37. PRIMAFRIO and KVC at Alhama city market during the survey implementation	54
Figure 38. Survey on market and business analysis by ICONS.....	55

Figure 39 Pictures of the Community-Based scheme	57
Figure 40 Seminar for the development of the Circular Game	57
Figure 41 Circular Game awards at PRIMA facilities	57
Figure 42. Videogames presented at DISTOPIA Festival	58
Figure 43. Final Agro2circular Video documentary. Link: https://youtu.be/pH1LYUV6alo .	59
Figure 44. Video pills published at A2C YouTube channel involving partners	59
Figure 45. Roundtable at CIRCULARMENTE event with participation of EVERSIA as A2C partner	60
Figure 46: A2C partners at CIRCULARMENTE event: INFO, REGENERA, GWC, AGROFOOD and EVERSIA	61
Figure 47. GWC and AGROFOOD representatives being interviewed during the CIRCULARMENTE event	61
Figure 48: Visit to the Cañada Hermosa waste management plant during the mentoring programme	62
Figure 49. Joint workshop with the HOOP project: Biowaste Club	65
Figure 50 Workshop at INFO	66
Figure 51. Screenshot of the 5th online workshop for validation of A2C model	67

List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
AGRO	Agrofood Cluster of the Region of Murcia
CARM	Autonomous Community of Region of Murcia
CE	Circular Economy
CEBM	Circular Economy Business Models
CETEC	Technological Centre for Plastic and Footwear of the Region of Murcia
CETENMA	Technological Centre for Energy and Environment of the Region of Murcia
CJM	CAJAMAR Foundation
CIFEA	Integrated Centre for Training and Agricultural Experiences
CTNC	National Technological Centre for Canning Industry
DoA	Description of the Action
Dn.n	Deliverable (number)
DEMn	Demonstrator number
DIS	Data Integration System
F2F	Face to face
IAP2	International Association of Public Participation
IDEE	Spanish Spatial Data Infrastructure
IDERM	Region of Murcia Spatial Data Infrastructure
INFO	Development Institute of the Region of Murcia
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KVC	KVELOCE
MCT	MOCITOS
Tn.n	Task (number)
M	Month of project
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PRIMA	Primafrio Foundation
PROEX	PROEXPORT (Fruit and Vegetable Exporters of the Region of Murcia)
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SP	Stakeholder Panel
TCA	Tecnoalimenti
Tn.n	Task (number)

UPCT Polytechnical University of Cartagena
UVEG University of Valencia
WPn Work Package (number)

Glossary

Description of the Action (DoA): In an H2020 and HE project, the DoA is a document that captures the essence of the envisaged solution including the project work plan and information regarding the project scope, cost, time and risks, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables, and project organisation and approach.

Face-to-face infrastructure: In the context of public participation processes, face-to-face participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room).

Public engagement: It is understood as the myriads of ways in which the activity and benefits of research can be shared with the public. Engagement is a two-way process involving interaction and listening aimed at generating mutual benefit at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower). The concept is considered a synonym for public participation and/or citizen engagement and all these terms will be used throughout the document.

Virtual infrastructures: In the context of public participation processes, virtual infrastructures comprise of online platforms, application software and collaborative channels that assist purposeful citizen engagement at all levels within a given territory (municipality, region, country, EU).

1 Executive summary <abstract>

The aim of D7.3 is to summarize the main outputs of the Public Engagement strategy put in place along the project implementation (M1-M36), including the activities performed during the extension (M36-M42) such as consultations and surveys to gather information from diverse stakeholders, and the set-up and management of participatory bodies. The initial Public Engagement Strategy was drafted in M12 (D7.1) and constituted a live document revised and updated at M24 (D7.2) of the project, to ensure adaptation to framework conditions and project progress. The design involves a four-steps process including ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication.

The A2C Public Engagement strategy is based on the Quadruple Helix of Innovation model and the Spectrum of Public Participation. The scope of the strategy was the regional level (Region of Murcia) and local level (Alhama de Murcia), to be complemented at EU scale by networking and clustering actions.

The ecosystem analysis required continuous revision and update along the project implementation to target the most relevant stakeholders in the engagement activities. For the diagnosis, only a few of the engagement infrastructures detected initially revealed as useful and sustainable after project completion. The Action Plan, encompassed 5 different levels: information (including webinars and seminars, open days, science fairs); consultation (through surveys and questionnaires for validating specific results or collecting feedback for the impact assessment), involvement (organising quizzes and videogames contests for students, roundtables and a mentoring programme for industry actors, a community-based scheme in a local market, or the shooting of a collective videodocumentary), and collaboration (by setting up 2 stakeholders panels, and organising co-creation workshops to deliver the multidimensional model of circular economy and the self-assessment tool). The empowerment level was reached indirectly, enhancing awareness and skills related to CE among the sectors involved and generating a favourable environment for active participation in the Region of Murcia.

The results could be sustained at the regional level, as public administrations and services as well as technological centres and clusters provide facilitating infrastructures and maintain long-term relationships with relevant stakeholders. At the EU level, adaptations may be required considering different political and governance contexts.

2 Introduction

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.3. Public Engagement summary of Activities and Results (Final) describing the actions and results of the A2C project undertaken within task 7.1.1 *Public engagement strategy*, updating D7.2 *Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results* launched in M24 (September 2023) with the activities implemented and the lessons learnt during the last year of the project.

For further understanding of this document, other related documents should be considered:

- The A2C project DoA, which is the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement number 101036838. It contains the details of how the action (project) should be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- The *Dissemination and Communication strategy* (D8.1, M4, January 2022), drafted under T8.1, aims at supporting the public engagement, spreading awareness and general knowledge and public awareness about food and plastic waste and the circular economy (CE) concept. It also includes guidelines for the communication focused on local and regional level, to be carried out in T8.3 (Communication and engagement at local and regional level) led by PRIMA.
- The *Evaluation framework and methodology* (D8.1, M9, June 2022) drafted in T7.2, provided guidelines for monitoring and assessment of the public engagement strategy and the transition towards circularity.
- The *Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report* (M41, February 2025) aims at assessing the impact of A2C project at macro level, focused on the sociocultural change created by the project's interventions along the project and particularly, the last year of implementation, considering participants' awareness, acceptance and behavioural change, hence ensuring that public engagement has been effectively achieved; and micro-level, assessing the impact of the technological developments achieved during the project in the social dimension.
- The *Toolkit of Guidelines and Training Materials-Final* (D8.7, M41, February 2025) represents the final version of the draft (D8.6, M18, March 2023), including lessons learnt and materials to promote CE at different educational levels (primary education, secondary education, vocational training and higher education), based on project results and methodologies, comprising community-based research, participatory methods and education for environmental issues as well as circular business models, financing and regulatory issues.

- The *Community-based innovation schemes* (D8.4, M41, February 2025) describes specifically the activities performed by PRIMAFRIO in a pilot community-based innovation action at local level in Alhama de Murcia (T7.1.2) together with a collection of community-based schemes performed in other projects and contexts, extracting lessons and best practices to promote circular social practices among citizens.
- A2C Systemic solution model and self-assessment tool (D7.10, M36, September 2024) includes the processes carried out for generating a multidimensional model designed for the adoption, replicability, and scalability of CE practices at regional and EU levels, including a self-assessment tool aimed at supporting cities and regions in evaluating their readiness to transition to a CE.

3 Agro2Circular Engagement Process

A2C Public Engagement strategy (D7.1) was designed following a four-steps process including ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication:

- i) **Ecosystem Analysis:** consists of a review of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders relying on the **Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders** model (Figure 1) for the public participation at the regional (Region of Murcia Autonomous Community) and local level (for the community-based innovation scheme in Alhama de Murcia). It has been summarized in [section 4](#) of this document.
- ii) **Diagnosis:** entailed the analysis of the Project actions according to the DoA, framed in

Figure 1 Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders

the 5 level of participation defined by IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation¹ (Figure 2), the needs and priorities of the region to deploy a CE, and the setup of the engagement infrastructure. It has been summarized in [section 5](#) of this document.

- iii) **Action Plan:** based on the existing resources and relevant actors, designed the participatory activities according to the level of participation entailed by the A2C

¹ <https://www.iap2.org/general/custom.asp?page=corevalues>

interventions at the regional and local level, aligned with the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity. The activities have been reported in [section 6](#) of this document.

- iv) **Dissemination and communication:** coordinated according to the Dissemination and Communication Strategy defined in D8.1, and the activities deployed under Task 8.3 (Local Outreach), a collection of communication measures were envisaged to ensure the meaningful adoption, replication & scalability of the A2C systemic solution model.

Figure 2 Spectrum of Public Participation. Source: *Vancouver Mayor’s Engaged City Task Force. Final Report.* (2014) based on IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation

4 Ecosystem Analysis

This section aims to analyse the existing citizen engagement infrastructures and processes, to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the A2C citizen engagement strategies in the region of Murcia. The use of these infrastructures in the A2C project will be further explained in the section diagnosis (section 5), and action plan (section 6). The ecosystem analysis covered two different levels (Figure 3).

a) Regional, as the Agro2Circular Project is focused on the implementation of a systemic solution for the upcycling of the most relevant residues in the agrofood sector (fruits, vegetables and multilayer plastics) that are produced and processed at the region of Murcia

Figure 3 Region of Murcia and the municipality of Alhama de Murcia. Source: IDERM

b) Local, as pilot activities for citizen engagement, namely a community-based scheme, have been carried out in the Municipality of Alhama de Murcia, in the centre of the region.

Moreover, the engagement strategy was complemented at EU level by the activity 8.5 (Networking and Clustering) led by EURADA.

4.1 Analysis of the Citizen Engagement Infrastructure [updated]

4.1.1 Regional Level

4.1.1.1 Virtual

Virtual infrastructures comprise online platforms, application software, and collaborative channels having as a purpose citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower), in the region and its municipalities.

Region of Murcia Participation Platform

The Region of Murcia participation platform (<https://participa.carm.es/>, Figure 4) responds to the regulation document (Law 12/2014 of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community) that recognises the rights of citizens to participate in public affairs and requests the implementation of measures and tools to articulate this participation, applied within the scope of public administration of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community and entities conforming the public sector. It is aimed at the Region's citizens as well as citizen organisations having the region as their main area of activity.

This technological platform is managed by CARM, concretely by the Office for Transparency and Citizen Participation (OTPC). It allows the diffusion, and the management of the citizen participation tools, promoting channels to interact with regional administrations in designing and evaluating public policies. The platform also includes links to different territorial scopes of participation, such as the municipalities, communities of citizens from Murcia in other Spanish regions and abroad, participation at the national and the EU level, as well as resources and information for associations. The platform also provides information on activities to promote citizen participation, such as workshops or funding.

The platform foresees 5 types of participative processes: citizen contributions, public consultations, participative deliberation processes, citizen participation forums and citizen initiatives. At the moment of writing this deliverable, there are no open participatory processes in the fields related to the project.

Figure 4. Citizen participatory platform (Region of Murcia)

The platform also communicates through Twitter/X using the account [@RMTransparencia](https://twitter.com/RMTransparencia) [Open Data Region of Murcia \[updated\]](https://www.opendataregionmurcia.es/)

This website (<https://datosabiertos.regiondemurcia.es/>), responds to the commitment of the Region of Murcia administration to join the Open Data Initiative. The website works at the Inform level, providing data on a wide range of indicators (environmental, social, economic). Data can be used to generate applications and services. Currently, two applications are already launched: AGROCLIMA (integrated management of meteorological data with open access for agricultural planning, developed by the Institute in Murcia for Agricultural Innovation and Research – IMIDA) and Agenda Regional – Region de Murcia Digital (for

mobile devices, providing information on next events extracted from the Region of Murcia digital portal, developed by an SME). Although there are no applications on the topics related to the CE, the platform includes a section where citizens can suggest the development of other services.

Although in previous versions of the Public Engagement Strategy it was foreseen that this space could also host the Data Integration System (DIS) generated within A2C, in the form of a link, this could not be accomplished as the platform is not under direct control of the CARM department involved in the project.

Nevertheless, both the website of the project as well as the public component of the DIS (<https://sat.agro2dis.eu>) has been linked hosted at the website of the Regional Ministry of Agriculture of the Region of Murcia ([https://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=933&IDTIPO=140&RASTRO=c80\\$m](https://www.carm.es/web/pagina?IDCONTENIDO=933&IDTIPO=140&RASTRO=c80$m), Figure 5) allowing stakeholders to evaluate the environmental readiness of their region focusing on waste and resource management in the Agrofood sector.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the SAT linked to the website of CARM ministry of Agriculture

[Open Knowledge Site of the Region of Murcia \[updated\]](https://conocimientoabierto.carm.es/)

URL: <https://conocimientoabierto.carm.es/>

It is an open access repository where documents are stored and disseminated using normalised protocols to ensure the visibility of the documents and their authors, in such a way they are findable by specialised and generalist search engines.

The repository was initiated as a training modality by the public administration school in 2011 and became a project for knowledge management in 2014 collecting digital contents

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from research, technical reports and other publications from the Region of Murcia. The website is currently coordinated by the transparency office of the Region of Murcia, while the document upload is overseen by designated persons in charge of each collection depending on the topics covered (Agriculture, Livestock and Fishing, Social Policies, European Union).

Although in previous versions of the Public Engagement Strategy it was foreseen that this space could also host a link to A2C Public Deliverables, this option has been dismissed due to a wide range of IPR aspects to be considered and the operation of the Open Data service by departments not directly linked to CARM units linked to the project.

As indicated above the link has been included in the Regional Ministry (Figure 5).

[Transparency Site of the Region of Murcia](#)

This website can be found at URL <https://transparencia.carm.es/>.

It responds to the obligation of the autonomous community to provide active advertising that is regularly updated and published without an explicit requirement by the citizenship, thus ensuring the transparency that constitutes the first level of public participation (Inform) regarding institutional and organisational information, relationships with society, regulations, contracts and agreements, grants and subsidies, as well as information on budgets, properties, assets, land planning and environment. The information provided refers to the public administrations, autonomous bodies, public entities, foundations, and consortiums. The website includes information on corporate and civic participation bodies, the regulatory frameworks governing them, their sessions and the agreements achieved. The transparency platform also includes links to the open data website and the participation website.

Other communication channels are:

- Twitter/X <https://twitter.com/RMTransparencia>
- YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnaWZAz4krBWI3GVcJw6wvA>

SITMURCIA: Geoportal of the Region of Murcia Spatial Data Infrastructure [updated]

Figure 6 SIT MURCIA (Geoportal) homepage

This service can be accessed at <https://sitmurcia.carm.es/> (Figure 6) Integrated into the Spanish Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDEE), the Region of Murcia Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDERM) provides georeferenced data on different thematic areas, that can be visualised (thus relevant for transparency and information) using a GIS visor (hosted) or WMS/WMTS services (Figure 6).

Figure 7 EIEL CARM showing equipment for urban waste management in Alhama de Murcia

Under the thematic area *Infrastructures and equipment*, the portal includes the Local Infrastructures and Equipment Survey (EIEL; https://geoportal.imida.es/eiel_carm/), a qualitative and quantitative analysis tool of the services under the competencies of municipalities, allowing the distribution of resources and the planning of public investments,

such as the location of waste management bins (paper/board, plastic, organic, batteries) as shown in Figure 7 for Alhama de Murcia.

This infrastructure was initially considered of interest for the engagement of local actors for the community-based scheme: for instance, to host the information on bins installed to collect food waste. Nevertheless, it was later discarded, due to the punctual allocation of the bins during the days when Task 7.1.2. was carried out the first year of the scheme. Instead, the location of the bins was informed to the market vendors.

Plataforma Tierra [updated]

The Plataforma Tierra (Tierra Platform, URL: <https://www.plataformatierra.es/>) is owned by the CJM non-profit foundation partner of the A2C Project, created by the Cajamar credit cooperative bank private funding entity. It is available in English.

The platform allows users to register as a user through a form, the compulsory fields being personal data (name, surname), the field of activity (Agriculture/Livestock, Industry and services, Knowledge, Public Bodies and Associations, Financing, Consumers, others) and fields of interest (including different types of crops and livestock species).

After registering, the platform offers a summary of upcoming events and meteorological predictions (Figure 8) as well as information on key agricultural indicators (market prices), links to videos and news.

Figure 8 Screenshot of Plataforma Tierra

In the top bar, the main menu is included with the following sections: **Markets**, **Innovation**, **Tools**, and **Training**.

Figure 9 Training section of Plataforma Tierra

It was initially considered to include a link to the A2C Data Integration System (DIS) in development under WP1 (Task 1.5) in the section Tools, and to offer courses under T8.6, aimed at different professionals and including technical and financial aspects of CE under section Training. Nevertheless, it is planned that the platform will finally host capacity building materials in the field of funding and webinars and seminars will be organized in the following months.

LOOPARM: Observatory of CE and Entrepreneurial Sustainability of the Region of Murcia
[New]

Figure 10. LOOPARM website

The Observatory of CE and Entrepreneurial Sustainability of the Region of Murcia (LOOPARM, <https://looparm.es>, Figure 10) was pushed forward by the Technological Centre of Energy and Environment of the Region of Murcia (CETENMA) with the collaboration of the CARM, INFO and backed by the Smart and Sustainable Strategy of the Region (RIS4, <https://www.ris4regiondemurcia.es/>). It is supported by the participation of different stakeholders representing academia (Polytechnical University of Cartagena, UPCT); private technological centres (Plastic and Footwear, CETEC; Canned Food, CTNC; Wood and Furniture, CETEM; Building, CTCÓN), Innovation and business centres from Murcia (CEEIM) and Cartagena (CEEIC) and entrepreneurial associations (FREMM). The website is available in Spanish.

Figure 11. LOOPARM Best practices indicator framework

LOOPA aims to establish alliances to foster circularity, to set up a network of agents, professionals and agents implementing activities to drive the circular transition, to promote skill acquisition and awareness raising on concepts related to CE, and to measure the progress of CE through a framework of indicators (Figure 11). It also includes a dynamic catalogue of best practices and R+D+i projects related to the CE, one of them being A2C (Figure 12), reflecting the [solutions for upcycling agrofood wastes](#).

In addition, the website offers dissemination articles on different practices related to CE, some of them have been implemented by A2C such as the Digital Product Passport (DPP), a glossary with basic concepts and a section with events.

Figure 12. A2C as success case at LOOPA dynamic catalogue

The LOOPA website has facilitated the participation of A2C project in several initiatives related to the promotion of the CE at regional level, particularly CIRCULARMENTE (further described in the Action Plan section, see page 60) and a Sectoral Club (see page 45) on the circular transition of the plastic sector.

4.1.1.2 Face-to-Face (F2F)

Face-to-face participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room) or virtually through teleconferences.

Sectoral Councils [updated]

Different types of collegiate bodies operate in the Region of Murcia, among which those related to the topics of A2C are mentioned. These bodies meet the requirement of the government (President, Vice-president, or Regional Councillors):

- **Regional Agricultural Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council of Agriculture Professional Organisations.**

- **Regional Environmental Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council of Social Economy:**

In addition, the following bodies are technical and consultative boards that provide qualified advice on the issues considered by the President or Vice-President:

- **Regional Consumption Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council on Citizen Participation.**

Initially, it was considered to present the A2C project in meetings of the Advisory Councils aforementioned, to increase the engagement of related stakeholders and ensure a wider acceptance of results, especially to promote CE in the agrofood sector. Nevertheless, the project has been finally presented at the Governance Board and General Assembly of PROEX, since it represents a wide number of farmers and agrofood industries in the region of Murcia.

4.1.2 Local Level

The Alhama de Murcia City Council published the Regulation on Citizen Engagement in 2012 (BORM 20/02/2012²) which details the processes and bodies involved. In the regulation, different levels of public participation are covered. In this way, the regulation sets the means and the channels for the Inform level, as well as the Consult level, through public surveys and questionnaires. In addition, it regulates the right to participation, through propositions, and the arrangement of public consultations and referendums. The regulation also foresees the foundation of associations and entities for public participation at the local level, the potential funding through subsidies, their inclusion in the local register of these associations, and their participation in local decision-making bodies.

In addition, the City Hall implemented the Strategy for Sustainable and Integrated Urban Development (EDUSI) 2017-2023, which includes a **specific plan for citizen engagement** collecting contributions from different social and economic agents, experts, technical and political staff and citizens, through meetings, forums and local assemblies, on specific topics and also transversal issues.

² <http://transparencia.alhamademurcia.es/transparencia-municipal/reglamento-de-participacion-ciudadana/>

Virtual [updated]

The website of the Councillorship of Public Participation³ offers different opportunities for public participation.

- **Participative budgets** (last process in 2021).
- **Agenda Urbana 2030:** the agenda has been developed to deploy the SDGs at the local level. A preliminary diagnosis was open in the form of an online form, until June 2022, to collect feedback from citizens on different topics, including environmental awareness, mobility, and waste recycling. Thereafter, the document Agenda Urbana was elaborated including an Action Plan and approved by the City Council in February 2023⁴.

Moreover, there is a website called Alhama Suma (<http://www.alhamasuma.es/>), directly related to the EDUSI, in which citizens can give their opinions on the strengths and weaknesses of the city in different areas: Environment and Climatic Change, Infrastructure and Services, Natural and Cultural Heritage, Society and Demography, Economy and Employment, and an additional space where citizens can provide suggestions.

Initially, it was considered to use the website of the City Hall to collect information of citizens from different social and economic agents, experts, technical and political staff and citizens, on awareness of CE and the implementation of CE practices. Nevertheless, the infrastructures of the project and particularly, the Spanish section of the A2C website were used throughout the project duration, since the City Hall website was not under direct control of the departments involved. Instead, as explained below, the F2F infrastructures were put at disposal of the project for meetings and holding permanent information.

Face-to-Face [updated]

The city of Alhama has two stable bodies for public face-to-face participation:

- The Local Council of Economy and Employment (since 1998) comprises 19 economic and labour organisations.
- The Local Assembly of Citizen Engagement (since 2012) comprises 26 neighbourhood associations and social organisations.

The participation infrastructures described were finally not considered in the A2C project; nevertheless, the City Hall was actively involved in the Community Based scheme through

³ <https://ayuntamiento.alhamademurcia.es/areas/area.asp?id=29>

⁴ <https://datos.alhamademurcia.es/descargas/918s-agenda-urbana-alhama-prediagnosticofeb22.pdf>

the Commerce department and the Local Development Agency, facilitating the installation of A2C booth at the local weekly Market for awareness raising campaigns and the implementation of surveys and interviews to measure the social impact within T7.4.

4.2 Stakeholders and Services

The stakeholders and services related to the engagement strategy in the Region of Murcia and the municipality of Alhama, which are relevant for A2C topics and according to the Quadruple Helix of Open Innovation, were mapped using different sources of information

- **Desk research:** comprising regional services and institutions, as well as the regional register of associations (especially those on agriculture, environment protection and consumers).
- **Consultations** with key stakeholders and experts in the region.

The result of the mapping exercise was included in D7.1, and as Annex in D7.2.

Sociograms were finally not developed within the participatory processes; instead, the list of key actors was regularly revised and updated, and during the workshops performed along the project (see [section 6. Action Plan](#)) the participants suggested stakeholders that may be contacted due to their potential interest and contributions.

5 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase defines the contextual basis for the action plan to be specified in the following section.

Based on the results of the [Ecosystem Analysis](#) performed, the bodies and spaces of participation that exist and are relevant for A2C co-creation processes, comprising institutional and private as well as those resulting from previous participatory processes, were selected. Subsequently, the levels of participation required by co-creation and citizen empowerment processes were analysed to determine the actions that are more appropriate for the [Action Plan](#). Finally, a set of virtual and face-to-face infrastructures that would be created to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) was proposed.

5.1 Selection of Existing Infrastructure [updated]

The analysis of the existing virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation at the regional and local levels resulted in the selection of those that could be used within A2C (Table 1), due to their relevance to the project topics (CE, Environmental Management, Social Economy, Public Engagement) and the scope of the project. For example, the provision of information, spaces for collecting feedback from civil society and fostering participation and collective decision.

Further key alliances were identified based on the analysis of the key stakeholders, getting at relevant actors related to circular economy, such as local associations of market vendors, village neighbourhoods (Gebas area, with projects related to environment) and environmental associations (La Almajara). Collaborative workshops with stakeholders (see section 6.1) were used as a tool to identify key alliances, action sets and feasibility. To this end, meetings were held at the Local Development Agency that borrowed their facilities and eased the contacts, and brochures were left in the Agency as an information point (see Table 1).

At the end of the project, the infrastructures that have been involved have been marked in black in Table 1, being the more relevant for the scope of the activities performed and controlled directly by project partners and collaborating entities.

Table 1 Virtual and face-to-face infrastructures

Type	Regional Level	Local Level
Virtual	Region of Murcia participation platform	Councillorship of Commerce and local development
	SIT Murcia (geoportal)	[updated]
	Open data platform	Alhama Suma
	Transparency site	
	Plataforma Tierra	
	LOOPARM	
Face-to-face	Regional Agricultural Assessment Council	Local Development Agency [updated]
	Regional Assessment Council of Agriculture Professional Organisations.	Local Council of Economy and Employment
	Regional Environmental Assessment Council	Local Assembly of Citizen Engagement
	Regional Consumption Assessment Council	
	Regional Assessment Council of Social Economy	
	Regional Assessment Council on Citizen Participation	

5.2 Preliminary Review

During the A2C kick-off meeting, the presentation of WP7 included three preliminary questions for the partners involved with their existing networks and participation channels that could be useful for the project. The answers obtained were used as a first step for the ecosystem analysis. As a result of this analysis, a preliminary SWOT matrix was elaborated (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Preliminary SWOT matrix: engagement processes for the implantation of the CE

At the end of June 2022 (M9) under WP7 activities (T7.1) a workshop was organized in Alhama de Murcia (where the coordinators and other partners are based) aiming at analysing the existing spaces for collaboration in the project. The activity is fully described in the Regional Workshop on Public Engagement ([section 6.1](#)).

5.3 Levels of Participation in A2C Activities [updated]

A2C has entailed a citizens’ engagement process in the Region of Murcia comprising different levels of participation, based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* developed by the International Association of Public Participation (IAP2), as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Levels of public participation.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>

The spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high participation, where stakeholders collaborate in the development of project deliverables through workshops.

The spectrum levels within the A2C project were:

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

Inform level only involves a one-way flow of information from the project to citizens, although it is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and take informed decisions. Some authors ([1], [2]) consider that the Inform level should be placed across the spectrum, since effective engagement requires effective information to fully understand the project's actions so that they can reach their own conclusions. This way, although informing does not involve community participation per se ([3], [4]), it increases the understanding of the issues, the ability of the stakeholders and communities to address them, and the compliance with regulations [5]. Hence, the Inform level is appropriate in situations where there is no opportunity for the public to influence decision-making. Simply informing them is the appropriate

activity. These activities overlap and are to be coordinated with those in WP8.

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed and will acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

The Consult level of public participation focuses on feedback and is the basic minimum opportunity for the public to input on analysis, alternatives or decisions. The responsibility for the decisions remains with the government or the organisations doing the consulting (i.e., the project manager). The Consult level is appropriate when specific input is sought from citizens for the decision-making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process. There is a wide range of ways to perform consultations, some of which include processes that require little or no dialogue (surveys in a newsletter or digital platform) or involve a debate (public meetings, focus groups). Several activities in the Region of Murcia have involved stakeholders (among them citizens) at the consultation level:

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

At the Involve level, citizens are invited into the process to a greater extent than at the Consult level. The goal is to work with the public throughout the process and to make use of their knowledge and expertise on a given issue. This implies a two-way exchange of information that encourages discussion while providing an opportunity to influence the outcome. The Involve level not only ensures a common understanding, but also the products or services provided are better tailored to the stakeholders' needs. The regulation, standardisation or

behaviour needs are accepted and sustainable and the resources are effectively applied at this level. However, while ‘Involve’ assumes a greater level of participation by stakeholders as they work through issues and alternatives to assist in the decision-making process, the organisation undertaking the engagement generally retains responsibility for the final decision.

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will seek direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions from you. Your advice and recommendations will be incorporated into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

At the Collaborate level, the public is directly engaged in decision-making in an interactive process with an emphasis on two-way processes. The Collaborate level of public engagement includes all the elements of Involve but takes it a step further, including an explicit attempt to find consensus solutions. However, similar to the Involve level of participation, the administration or project management board remains the ultimate decision-maker.

The main challenge of this level is to create trust and to ensure that there is genuine engagement, which is often costly and time-consuming. Besides, there can be risks involved in processes at this level. If the promise is seen as being broken (e.g., if members of a community cannot agree on ways forward, or if some sections of the community feel their views were not taken into account), trust can be broken and future relationships with key stakeholders can be significantly damaged. The Collaborate level is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation.

Citizen engagement goal: To place final decision-making into the hand of the public.

Promise to the public: We will implement what you decide.

At the Empower level, the public has the opportunity to make decisions for themselves, which implies a shared responsibility for making

decisions and accountability for the outcomes of these decision. Empower represents the most challenging approach in community engagement, since it represents a commitment by the initiators (administration, government, project management board) to participate as a stakeholder and to share power in decision-making for collaborative actions [1].

5.4 A2C Virtual and Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]

5.4.1 A2C Virtual Infrastructure [updated]

In addition to the already existing participation infrastructures mentioned in section 4.1, the following virtual channels and sites have been used for the A2C public engagement.

Web platforms

- **A2C website (<https://agro2circular.eu>)** – active, managed by ICONS as WP8 leader. The website homepage (Figure 15) includes information on the project (why, what, how, where, who), resources to download (deliverables, flyers, postcards), and news at EU level. It is linked to the Spanish version through the menu.

Figure 15. A2C website homepage (What? section) in English

- **A2C local website** (<https://agro2circular.eu/es/>): it was deployed by ICONS as Dissemination and Communication Level in May 2022, managed by PRIMA as partner leading the local outreach desk, and KVC responsible for the engagement strategy, while other partners (CETEC, PROEX, AGRO, DMC, CTNC) have also provided information and news for the local website. The Spanish section of the A2C website reproduced the general project website, with news related to the activities carried out at the regional level such as the pilot demonstrators, the community-based scheme, and events such as workshops and mentoring activities, forums and consultations, avoiding linguistic barriers (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Event created for the collaboration with Biowaste Club of HOOP project in April 2023

Current status

Two types of publications were used at the A2C local website:

- **Events:** This category was used to announce future events and activities, in which the public is called to participate.
- **News:** News pieces are uploaded once the activities have taken place, summarising the main results and conclusions.

- **Social networks:** The Twitter channel (@Agro2Circular) and the **official hashtag** #agro2circular have been set by ICONS, as well as the LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/agro2circular>).

Current status

According to D8.1, a Twitter profile (@Agro2Circular) and the official hashtag #agro2circular, as well as the LinkedIn profile were set and managed by ICONS, offering information in English language; at the local level, publications in these social media were shared by the partners in their own accounts (mainly PRIMA and KVC but also CETEC, AGRO, DMC, EVERSIA) in Spanish, tagging the projects' profile and those of collaborating partners to ensure a wider dissemination.

In April 2023, a Youtube Channel was opened, in which short videos were uploaded depicting the multidisciplinary scope of the project, the role of different stakeholders in the CE related to the agrifood sector, and the video documentary produced by PRIMA. Up to date, 22 videos have been uploaded.

The impact of these activities is explained in detail in the Dissemination and Communication report.

5.4.2 A2C Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]

Different structures and spaces for public participation were created within the A2C Project.

- **A2C Space at the regional level:** This space was aimed at providing information on the project and the systemic circular solution of A2C. The local outreach desk deployed a stand at the local market (near the zones dedicated for food stalls, see Figure 17 and Inform paragraph in section 6.2.1) on a regular basis, where information on the project was provided and the activities were carried out. A request was also made to Alhama de Murcia Town Hall for a space in the Town Hall of Alhama de Murcia, as a supporting entity where participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings would be held, constituting the office of the local outreach desk.

Current status

Up to the launch of this Final Report, information regarding the project (brochures and flyers) were available at the Local Development Office of the Alhama de Murcia City Council. This office has also hosted meetings with stakeholders for the preparation of Task 7.1.2 and the implementation of interviews for the socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis (T7.4). As space limitation did not allow full dedication to A2C, the information was present in a corner together with other projects, which contributed to generating synergies with environmental initiatives.

The local outreach desk at the Alhama City market was in function during two different periods:

- i) From November 2023 (M14) to June 2023 (M21), a booth was installed every 2 weeks at the Alhama city market within the activity T7.1.2. This booth acted as a space fully dedicated to the project, where information was shared using brochures and flyers, samples of upcycled products were distributed to citizens, and a raffle was held among the participants in questionnaires and surveys on CE practices. The booth was accompanied by 6 containers, in which the waste of fruit of vegetables (apple, broccoli, cauliflower, lemon, and grape) was collected during the community-based scheme further explained in D7.4. The activity was interrupted during the summer months, due to the high temperatures (weather alerts).
- ii) From October 2023 (M25) to April 2024 (M31), the booth constituting A2C local space was present at the Alhama City market, on a monthly basis. During this period, the containers were not installed due to logistical constraints, and the booth was reoriented to raise awareness on the importance of CE practices and collect the feedback of visitors on the topic and potential acceptance of the products through questionnaires and surveys.

Furthermore, the networking activities carried out by the project have also allowed the availability of spaces for the organization of participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings, such as the Circular Education Lab in Murcia, aimed at the awareness raising and the widespread of circular practices.

- **Coordination and Management Group:** This group was composed of the partners responsible for the public participation methodology of the project, who established agile and flexible governance systems to ensure the smooth communication and coordination towards all stakeholders (policy makers, industry, research and education, and citizens). The

coordination and management group coordinated the different bodies created for the engagement process and acted as mediator in case any controversy arises.

Current status

The Coordination and Management Group was set up by KVC and PRIMA. They have held regular meetings (approx. 1 per month, online) to supervise the performance of the activities being carried out as part of the Public Engagement, and to coordinate the Local and Regional Dissemination and Communication according to the project needs, ensuring wider outreach. CETEC as project coordinator has supported this coordination and management group, providing advice and means to achieve the desired objectives (contacts, requirements to partners, information).

- **Driving Group:** This group was built in September 2022 after the CE workshop held in Alhama de Murcia in June 2022. Their main objectives were to generate synergies with other existing and ongoing projects at the local and regional level, organising activities, seeking mutual support, and detecting solutions for the implantation of the circular systemic solution.

Current status

The Driving Group acted as part of the local stakeholder panel set up for the project. It was composed by partners based in the region of Murcia: Regional Development Agency (INFO), Industry (AGRO, PROEX, CJM), Research (CETEC, CTNC) and public Administration (CARM), together with KVC (Systemic Approach Manager) and PRIMA (Local Outreach Manager).

During the project implementation, five workshops were organised, further detailed in the Action Plan (Collaboration level).

6 . Action Plan

6.1 Regional Workshop on Public Engagement [updated]

Under WP7, a regional workshop on public engagement at the regional level was organised in June 2022 at CETEC facilities in Alhama de Murcia to establish a participatory approach toward the stakeholders' needs and priorities. It was organised to identify the interest, opinions, and wishes of the partners involved in WP7 at the regional level and to detect potential infrastructures and analyse synergies and barriers. The workshop represented a key point for organising the community-based scheme. Moreover, this workshop served to nurture further public engagement activities.

Current status

The workshop was organized by KVC and attended by CETEC, PRIMA, AGRO, PROEX, CJM, and CARM, constituting the first meeting of the Driving group.

During the workshop, participative methodologies were used to explore the opportunities for engagement at the regional and local scales. First, shared in groups their interests and prospects, based on the 5 levels of engagement of the IAP2; thereafter, during a plenary session, the proposed activities were displayed on a panel (Figure 18). Most of the activities were framed in the inform, consult and involve levels. During this session, the infrastructures of public engagement in A2C were also discussed. These results were already reflected in D7.1, as the activities to be carried out at the different levels of IAP2.

Figure 18 Panel of opportunities for public engagement

Subsequently, another plenary session was conducted to explore barriers and framework conditions for the engagement activities (Figure 19).

Figure 19 Plenary session

Among the aspects to be considered, the following should be highlighted:

- The need of dynamizing the Spanish section of the website, to constitute an effective tool for engagement (implemented: see [5.4.1 Virtual A2C infrastructures](#)).

- A framework condition that may difficult the involvement of agrifood companies was the legal definition of waste according to Law 7/2022 for waste and contaminated soil⁵, which considers waste as materials that an agent discards or has the intention to discard. This definition leaves out outgrades from the agrofood sector that are already used in the canning industry or food for livestock and should not be considered “waste”. At this regard, it has been encouraged the use of the terms that replace “waste” (for instance, outgrades or secondary raw materials) in subsequent deliverables, such as policy recommendations, to avoid the negative implications of the term waste, that also affects the acceptability of products generated by the public.
- Regarding the multilayer plastics used for mulching, partners called attention to the inconsistencies related to the types that are being recommended and subsidized by regional authorities, although they are not biodegradable. This issue will be analysed by the competent authorities.
- The availability of some agrifood “waste” is limited in time by seasonality. The suggestion of exploring other types of food waste is subject to technical justification. At the end, the types of outgrades and secondary raw materials were maintained, since expanding would imply additional workload for technical partners, out of the scope of the project, due to the specificity of extraction routes and other types of fruits or vegetables will be explored in projects derived from Agro2Circular.
- The need of communicating financial and economic aspects, beyond technical dimensions, targeting professionals and companies through dedicated training was also underlined. This aspect has been covered in the financial recommendations delivered in the project (D7.14, March 2023 and D7.15, March 2025).

6.2 Public Engagement Activities [updated]

6.2.1 Inform level [updated]

Information on the website and social media: As indicated before (section 5.4.1), a Spanish section of the website was created in October 2022. Along with the project implementation, 37 News pieces (Figure 20) and 8 Events (Figure 21) have been published on the local website. Further information is provided in D8.3 (Dissemination and Communication Final Report, M42).

⁵ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2022-5809>

Next steps

The activity at the website and social media will be maintained after the project completion, with the aim at dynamizing the contents and sharing the final results.

Some of the planned news that are pending to be published in the last month will be the Final Event organised by the coordinator CETEC in March 2025, with the collaboration of other partners such as CTNC, KVC, GWC, and INFO.

It is also expected to publish the best practices regarding community-based social innovation schemes for CE (gathered as part of D7.4) , in an appealing format to reach a wider public.

Figure 20. Last news published at A2C local website

Figure 21. Events published at the local website

Webinars and seminars. The organization of webinars and seminars has been focused to educational purposes, and carried out by PRIMA, KVC, CETEC and AGRO aimed at the different levels (primary and secondary schools, vocational education and university). Three different topics have been addressed so far: a general seminar on CE, and two specific seminars on plastic upcycling and the application of biotechnology to CE. The seminars at educational centres were performed during two scholar years

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

2022/2023	2023/2024
February 2023-May 2023	October 2023- May 2024
9 different educational centres	6 educational centres
16 Workshops/seminars	26 Workshops/seminars
726 students	1108 students reached

Furthermore, other seminars and webinars were organised targeting different stakeholders, such as professionals or enterprises, to engage them in the implantation of the CE, with the participation of CETEC, KVC, AGRO, CTNC and GWC. Some examples are:

- A webinar organized by the Technological Centre on Environment of the Region of Murcia (CETENMA) and AGRO in a webinar organized by the University of Alcalá - Analytical Chemistry area in the subject "Use of waste from the food industry".
- Participation in two “Agrofood working days” to share innovative projects organised by AGRO (9th May 2024 at Polytechnical University Cartagena and 14th November 2024 at University of Murcia)

Figure 22. Agrofood working day in Cartagena

Figure 23. Agrofood working day in Murcia

- Webinar Sectoral Club “Circular Transition in the Plastic Sector”: it was held on 28th May 2024 with experts and representatives of industry, to discuss the benefits of CE. The event, organized by INFO and CETENMA, as part of the LOOPARM observatory, comprised technical sessions and showcasing success cases, and counted with presentations by CETEC, entrepreneurial

approaches by PRIMA, GWC and CETECBIO; and presented funding opportunities and best practices (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Poster of the webinar

- A Workshop on Implementation of CE Business Models in Valencia and the use of the DIS (September 2024), taught by PRIMAFRIO and CETEC, within a CCRI Event (Figure 25)

Figure 25. Workshop on circular business models at CCRI

- A workshop organised by CETEC in November 2024 with students of Industrial Engineering degrees at Polytechnical University in Cartagena (UPCT) in which the sustainability requirements for plastic packaging were described (Figure 26)

Figure 26. CETEC during the workshop at UPCT

Next steps

A Lecture is planned by CETEC at the University of Murcia on 28th February 2025. Moreover, a Webinar has been planned, as part of the Final Event foreseen in March 2025, under the title “**Showing the results of circular systemic solutions for agri-food industry and the link with regional bioeconomy**”. It will be hosted by INFO, to present the advances developed during the project and the lessons learnt, delivering recommendations for the replication in other regions and subsectors. As the webinar will provide the opportunity to attend both face-to-face and online, it will ensure the participation of EU stakeholders and the collaboration of other projects of the CE, thus fostering networking and creation of synergies. The agenda and dissemination materials are in preparation at the time of launching this deliverable.

Expositions and attendance to events. All along the project, partners have been participating in expositions and scientific and technical events, raising the awareness of the public from all sectors of the stakeholder helix on the challenges addressed by A2C and the solutions proposed to achieve the circularity of the agrifood sector. Some examples of this activity are:

- Science Week, an event held in Murcia at the end of October each year, organised by Fundación Seneca, in which the technological centres CTNC and CETEC were present in the 3 years of the project (2022, 2023 and 2024) together with AGRO and PRIMAFRIO (Figure 29 and Figure 30) while CJM participated in the Science Week held in Almeria in November 2023 organised by the local University, as well as the Researchers Night in September 2024 (Figure 33);

- CJM also presented a poster at the “Challenges of Bioeconomy in Andalusia and Spain” Conference in May 2024. The Conference took place at the Scientific-Technologic Park of Almeria (PITA) and was also attended by the partner DMC. The poster of the project was shown to companies and entities in the agrofood sector (Figure 27).
- CJM organized a Conference in October 2024 “Cajamar Talent Area Conference” at the

Figure 27. A2C poster at the "Challenges of bioeconomy" conference.

headquarters in Estación Experimental Las Palmerillas in Almeria, attended by 50 attendants from Cajamar branch network, primarily from the territorial divisions of Almería, Murcia, Málaga, Alicante and Extremadura, in which A2C goals were presented (Figure 28).

Figure 28. Photos of Cajamar Talent Area Conference

- [Innovam+22](#) held in Cartagena attended by AGRO and CTNC in October 2022;
- Attendance and presentation of results at National and International congresses in 2022, 2023 and 2024, such as CONAMA (Environment Congress in Spain); Murcia FOOD Brokerage Event organized by INFO in collaboration with CTNC in May 2023 (Figure 31); Crecestartup Agrifoodtech held online June 2023 with the participation from AGRO and CTNC; or [FAME- INNOWA fair](#) attended by PROEX in April 2023 and 2024.
- [FRUITLOGISTICA](#), attended by PROEXPORT in February 2023 and 2024 in Berlin, where A2C results were explained to agriculture professionals.
- FRUITATTRACTION, attended by PROEXPORT and PRIMA in October 2022 (Torre Pacheco, Murcia), 2023 and 2024 (Madrid), explaining A2C Goals to professionals
- CTNC together with Agrofood have organized an Event on 11th February 2025, in which the [Catalog of Best practices for CE for the Agrofood sector](#) was presented Further information on these activities can be found in the Dissemination and Communication Final Report (D8.3; M42).
- PROEXPORT has held diverse meetings among their associates (General Assembly September 2022 in Aguilas, February 2023 in Torre Pacheco, and June 2024 in Murcia, together with the Governance Board held April 2024 in Murcia).

Figure 29. Exposition on multilayer films at CETEC/CTNC booth. Murcia Science Week 2022

Figure 30. Food and nutraceutical compounds at CTNC booth during Science Week 2024

Figure 31. Murcia FOOD Brokerage Event 2023

Figure 32. CETEC presenting A2C at CONAMA 2024

Figure 33. CJM at the Researchers' Night 2024 in Almeria

Figure 34. PROEX at FRUITATTRACTION 2024

Site visits. Up to date, CETEC has already performed site visits (called Open Days) coinciding with the Green Week (June 2023, Figure 35), specially dedicated to young people and to students in the region from primary and secondary schools, vocational training and university degrees with close relationships to the project's topics (CIFEAs, environmental sciences, biotechnology, chemistry, agricultural/industrial/chemical engineering, to mention some).

Figure 35. Students during an Open Day at CETEC, Green Week 2023

Moreover, during the General Assembly held in October 2024 in Granada, DMC organised visits to the demonstrator at their facilities (DEM4 from those described in WP6 for extracting polyphenol from lemon waste and elaborating food additives), allowing the public (particularly industrial stakeholders and industry, but also researchers and public administrations) to fully understand the actions' features and implications.

Next steps

Figure 36. Demonstrator 4 at DMC Facilities. Site visit during General Assembly in October 2024

During the Final Event to be carried out in March 2025, an Open Day is being organised consisting on site visits to the demonstrators (**DEMs**) are planned in 3 different locations: Alhama de Murcia (**DEM1**-First recycling plan of plastic Multilayer materials at GWC, **DEM2**-Building blocks production from PE and PET hydrolysates for cosmetic uses at CETEC; **DEM5** -PHBV and carotenoids production at CETECBIO) and Molina de Segura (**DEM3**-Extraction of high added value substances from fruit and vegetable wastes at CTNC). They will be offered to the project partners, but also external stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix of Innovation (industry and private investors/funding entities, researchers and education sector, public administrations and civil society representatives) at regional level. In addition, videos will be recorded about all the demonstrators, also comprising those that for logistical challenges cannot be showcased during the event: **DEM4**-High added-value extracted substances from agrifood residues by green extraction +enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction + microwave; **DEM6**-Bioplastic PHBV compounds for packaging, **DEM7**-Recycled and recyclable high barrier compounds for food packaging, **DEM8**- Bioplastic PHBV compounds for agricultural mulching applications and **DEM9**- Recycled and recyclable high barrier compounds for agricultural applications), Murcia (**DEM2**-Building blocks from PE and PET for cosmetic uses, **DEM5** -PHBV and carotenoids production and **DEM10**- Digital Integration System. The videos will be disseminated through WP8 activities.

6.2.2 Consult [updated]

Socioeconomic Analysis: Under T7.4, the socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis required the participation of the stakeholders participating in two of the value chains addressed in the project (lemon pulp and peel, and disinfection film); the analysis is embedded in the evaluation framework, using the social organizational Lifecycle assessment (SO-LCA) approach. For the screening stage, a questionnaire was answered by 115 workers of the partners involved in the value chains described, and the results were reflected in the Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (D7.8; M18). A parallel consultation was run targeting stakeholders' managers, while VTT collected information for the environmental LCA (T7.3) and UB for the Lifecycle Cost Analysis (T7.4, results reflected in D7.8). It is worth highlighting that the questionnaire included different sets of questions, aimed at analysing the awareness and consciousness regarding CE, through selected questionnaires, as well as the environmental concern measured using the revised NEP (New Ecological Paradigm) scale ([6], [7]). Subsequently, from September to December 2024, the second stage of the Social Impact Evaluation (SOLCA) was performed, framed within T7.4. KVC designed questionnaires and interviews for different types of stakeholders: a) teachers participating in the video game contest and seminars; b) representatives of public administrations at local and regional level; c) representatives of industry participating in site visits and mentoring activity; c) market vendors and citizens involved in the community-based scheme in Alhama de Murcia. The content of the interview was adapted, depending on their participation level in the project and also taking in consideration accessibility issues to ensure participation of vulnerable groups (easy language, avoiding digital technologies to overcome the digital gap). For the case of the participants in the community-based scheme, the participation was rewarded with cosmetic products and

biodegradable bags similar to those produced in the project. These methodologies complemented the questionnaires fulfilled by managers and workers from A2C partners, and the detailed methodology and results of the Final Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis are described in T7.9 (M42, March 2025).

Survey at the community-based scheme: In addition to the survey mentioned above, PRIMAFRIO implemented a survey in April 2023 embedded in Task 7.1.2, aiming at further

Figure 37. PRIMAFRIO and KVC at Alhama city market during the survey implementation

engage the public in the implementation of CE and the A2C model while collecting their feedback on the activities. To optimize the participation, citizens were rewarded, for which specific merchandising materials were collected and the respondents of the survey participated in a raffle with a prize consisting of fresh fruits and vegetables.

Other consultations. Other surveys have been performed along the project implementation:

- For the co-creation of the multidimensional model (Task 7.5), a survey and an interview was fulfilled by 24 participants (partners and members of the Regional Stakeholder panel, see [Collaborate Level](#)) previous to the Workshop in July 2023. The surveys and interview consisted of a series of statements encompassing the 8 dimensions of the A2C model, environmental, technological, socioeconomic, financial, regulatory, governance, training and awareness raising, and standardisation).
- For the elaboration of the Training Materials (T8.6), an online survey was designed by UVEG targeting stakeholders from academia and education but also industrial stakeholders (companies and professionals) and public administrations. The objective was to collect

insights on the types of materials and the contents considered priorities for the final version of the Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (D8.7; M35).

- Framed in the Exploitation Strategy (T8.7), ICONS published an online survey at the website in October 2024, targeting experts from different industries to provide feedback on market trends, needs and opportunities in sustainable product development, connecting the advances of the project with real-world market demands in the sector of bioplastics, food additives and cosmetics (Figure 38). The results of the survey served to enrich the market and business analysis included in the Final Exploitation Strategy (D8.5, M41).
- A Survey on Policy recommendations was elaborated by UVEG in November 2024, to

Figure 38. Survey on market and business analysis by ICONS

collect information from EU stakeholders on the policy dimension of the A2C Model. The survey included a wide range of statements proposing policy measures to promote CE in the agrofood and plastic sectors, that was sent by email by UVEG, EURADA and KVC to the members of the A2C stakeholder panels and other representatives of industry and public administrations to be prioritised by the respondents prior to the organisation of a dedicated Workshop in December 2024. The results of the survey, refined during the workshop, are included in the Policy Briefs Final version (D7.13, M41)

6.2.3 Involve level [updated]

Community based scheme. Under task 7.1.2, a participative and community-based innovation (T7.1.2) has been organised by PRIMA, with the collaboration of KVC, CETEC, CTNC, AGRO, MCT and EVERSIA, to foster the acceptance, awareness and knowledge of climate-neutral practices, alternatives, and behaviours but also aimed at strengthening

communities, paying special attention to the challenges that disadvantaged and deprived communities may face. After preparatory meetings with the Alhama de Murcia City Council (particularly, the Local Development Department), and associations of market vendors, the activity started in November 2022. During the first year (November 2022 to May 2023), the scheme consisted of the installation of a booth at the City Market, that acted as A2C Face2face infrastructure (see section 0), and 6 containers in which the market vendors deposited the 6 types of fruit and vegetable waste considered in the project, to be sent to CTNC for further processing and incorporation to the A2C value chains (Figure 39). After summer break, the activity continued from November 2023- May 2024, but only installing the booth at the market, while the containers were not installed due to logistical constraints that diffculted the collection of fruit and vegetable waste for upcycling. The community-based scheme has also served to distribute surveys and questionnaires to measure the social impact of A2C, organize awards, and present products similar to those that will be the final products delivered in the project. The results and the lessons learnt are included in the *Community based innovation schemes report* (D7.4, M42) elaborated by PRIMA.

Figure 39 Pictures of the Community-Based scheme

Circular game award. [Circular Game](#) was an initiative to teach young people (Primary and secondary education) about the CE in a fun and engaging way, creating videogames related to the CE using the software Arkade Makecode. With this aim, more than 300 students from different centres in Alhama and Murcia joined in groups in each of the two editions (2023 and 2024) to create videogames after receiving a series of seminars in their educational centres from February to May (Figure 40). At the end of the activity the videogames designed were presented to take part in a **big contest** on CE videogames. After the evaluation of the videogames by a multidisciplinary jury, considering criteria related to the presence of circularity concepts, design and usability, the winners were awarded in a ceremony celebrated at PRIMA facilities in May 2023 (Figure 41). In 2024, the awarded videogames were presented as a parallel activity at the Festival DISTOPIA of Cinema and Environment performed in Murcia (Figure 42. Videogames presented at DISTOPIA Festival Figure 42).

Figure 40 Seminar for the development of the Circular Game

Figure 41 Circular Game awards at PRIMA facilities

Figure 42. Videogames presented at DISTOPIA Festival

Video documentary. Since January 2023, the local outreach desk has been collaborating in the elaboration of a collaborative video documentary. As a first step, a script was drafted to plan the contents, consisting of an introduction about the context of the project, the description of the different value chains addressed by the project, and finally different interviews with stakeholders in which the multidimensional aspect of the CE and the challenges and impacts for implementation are reflected through their impressions.

Led by PRIMAFRIO, the documentary started the shooting stage in March 2023, and the final result was uploaded to the website in October 2024 (Figure 43).

Figure 43. Final Agro2circular Video documentary. Link: <https://youtu.be/pH1LYUV6alo>

In the meantime, 14 information pills corresponding to the interviews section have been uploaded to the project Youtube channel (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Video pills published at A2C YouTube channel involving partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

CIRCULARMENTE Event. LOOPA regional observatory presented a Dynamic Catalog of best practices in CE, during the I CIRCULARMENTE event on entrepreneurial sustainability held in October 2024, organised by INFO. The event was focused on social impact, good governance and environment, and comprised roundtables (Figure 45) and networking sessions, in which tools to elaborate policies for sustainability were presented and the Agro2Circular project was showcased as a best practice ([see Link in Spanish](#)).

Moreover, during the event, INFO presented a Map of the CE for the business sector in the Region of Murcia. The document, [available online in Spanish at INFO's website](#), was elaborated through a participative process including interviews to business representatives and technological centres and the supervision of experts in CE. The document makes an exhaustive analysis of the status of the CE at the regional level, taking into consideration the existing EU and national policies and strategies, as well as the alignment with the regional development strategy, [RIS4 Region of Murcia](#). Likewise, among its contents, the proposition of governance measures to enhance transparency and participation, facilitate industrial synergies and promote circular requirements in public procurements should be highlighted.

Figure 45. Roundtable at CIRCULARMENTE event with participation of EVERSIA as A2C partner

Figure 46: A2C partners at CIRCULARMENTE event: INFO, REGENERA, GWC, AGROFOOD and EVERZIA

Figure 47. GWC and AGROFOOD representatives being interviewed during the CIRCULARMENTE event

Mentoring programme. Framed within the Training, Knowledge transfer and guidelines to promote the A2C circular model (T8.6), PRIMAFRIO in collaboration with CETEC, CTNC, PROEX, AGRO, KVC and UVEG developed an industry mentoring programme targeting companies from the Agrofood and plastic packaging sector.

Figure 48: Visit to the Cañada Hermosa waste management plant during the mentoring programme

The programme was implemented along 9 sessions (20 hours, mixed with face to face and online sessions) including seminars on the CE and the relationship with the SDGs, the identification of projects implemented, the generation of innovative business ideas based on CE principles, field visits (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and the elaboration of a project on business circularity. The programme took place between February and September 2024 (with a summer break during July and August 2024)

6.2.4 Collaborate level [updated]

Set up a stakeholder panel. After the mapping of stakeholders (first step of the Engagement Strategy drafting), several rounds of contact were performed to set up the stakeholder panel. The members were selected to represent the sectors related to the A2C (agrifood sectors, plastic recycling, packaging, agriculture, biotechnology, bioeconomy & CE, environment, policy makers, SSH & gender), and the different parts of the quadruple helix of innovation (Figure 1). To ensure the manageability, 2 different panels were created, each of them composed by 8 experts (2 from public administration, 2 from the industry, 2 from civil society and 2 from research and education). The aim of the regional panel (Table 2) was to collaborate with the Consortium during the project developments, for instance the detection of challenges and needs or the design of the A2C multidimensional model through cocreation workshops (task 7.5) while avoiding language barriers. The EU stakeholder panel

(Table 6) has a parallel composition and is involved in the validation of the multidimensional model for the adoption and scale up, and the elaboration of policy reviews (under task 7.7). The members of the Stakeholders Panels have signed a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA), together with the A2C coordinator, to certify their participation, ensure the fulfilment of ethical aspects and data protection requirements. The activities of the Stakeholder Panel have no related costs and are considered in-kind contributions. The list of EU stakeholders changed slightly (highlighted with color background in Table 3), due to position shifts of the participants and the right of withdraw included in the NDA, that required the reinforcement with additional actors.

Table 2 Regional stakeholder panel

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Level	Description/Rationale
Public Administration	Integrated Centre for Training and Agricultural Experiences Molina de Segura (dependent of Regional Ministry of Agriculture)	Organization of complementary and specialized training courses and actions, of regional, national and international scope, with the aim of updating and perfecting the technical skills of professionals in the sector. Participation in research through demonstrations at their facilities.
Public Administration	Alhama de Murcia City Council (Municipal level)	Department of Local Development and Commerce
Industry	AEMA (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia)	Environmental Businesses Association Region of Murcia. Including waste management, environmental consultancy, environmental quality, etc.
Research/Academia	Water eco-efficiency chair (Regional level)	University of Murcia
Research/Academia	Department of Tribology and materials	Polytechnical University Cartagena

Research/Academia	CETENMA (Regional level)	Environment research centre (private non for profit)
Civil Society	Ambiente Europeo (Regional level)	Specialized in CE and pollutions issues, collaboration with industries
Civil Society	Ecologistas en Acción Región Murciana	Environmentalist association with experience on impacts of with agrifood sector

Table 3. EU Stakeholder Panel.

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Level	Description/Rationale
Consumer Association	Unione Nazionale Consumatori Umbria (Italy)	Unione Nazionale Consumatori (UNC) is the first consumer association in Italy.
Industry	Spanish Food and Drink Federation FIAB-FOOD4LIFE	Association of Spanish industry for food and drinks, member of the EU federation of food and drink associations. Experience supporting R+D, publishes documentation on food security and sustainability of food and drink industries
Industry	FILSE SPA (Italy)	Regional development agency Liguria (Italy) supports region (public administrations) in development of policies and interventions
Industry	Agrotransilvania Cluster (Romania)	Technology transfer centre of RDI in agro-industrial field at national level.
Research/Academia	Holland Circular Hotspot	Private Research foundation that aims to accelerate the international transition to a CE through networking activities and knowledge change.

Research/Academia	Aalborg University (Denmark)	Packaging technology, packaging machinery and press-forming, heat sealing and converting of fibre-based materials.
Public Administration	Municipality of Nea Smyrni (Greece)-	Deputy Mayor. Implementation of circular projects related to food waste.

Workshops. Along the A2C project, 5 workshops were organised, consisting of different co-creation activities:

1. The **first workshop** served to validate the ecosystem analysis of the engagement strategy and draft the actions to be performed in the following months. The results of this workshop are detailed in section 6.1.
2. The **second workshop** was organised jointly with the [HOOP project](#), as one of the Biowaste Clubs that take part in the city of Murcia, hosted by the Circular Education Lab (Figure 49). The workshop aimed at addressing the challenges that the regional industry faces to implement the circular bioeconomy and identify opportunities for collaboration. Regional partners of the project (CETEC, KVC, CTNC, SOLPLAST, GWC, MCT, PROEX, INFO) attended the workshop (Figure 25, together with stakeholders (UPCT, CETENMA and Science for Change-SfC). The workshop also highlighted the importance of collaboration and synergies between different actors and the need for development and improvement of cutting-edge technologies, to fill the existing gaps in circular value chains.

Figure 49. Joint workshop with the HOOP project: Biowaste Club

Figure 25.

3. The **third workshop** was held on July 7, 2023, at the headquarters of the INFO in Murcia. In this workshop, organised jointly by KVC and UVEG (Figure 50), organizations and companies represented in the workshop were members of the Driving Group (CETEC, CJM, PRIMA, INFO, MCT, Regenera, GWC, EVERSIA, AGRO) and the regional Stakeholder

Panel (CETENMA, AEMA, UPCT, CIFEA, Alhama Municipality and Ecologistas en Acción). During the workshop, the results of the survey carried out electronically between June 15 and June 26, 2023, were presented, with the objective of gathering in first-hand the feedback of the participants about the results and validate with them the generalization of the multidimensional model that is being developed under T7.5, through the decontextualization of the statement of the items. The dimensions treated were: Environmental, Socioeconomic, Technological, Governance, Regulatory, Financial, Standardization and Training. For each dimension there were a series of items (challenges) that were assessed on the basis of the relevance for the adoption of the CE.

Figure 50 Workshop at INFO

4. The fourth workshop was focused on the policy and governance dimension of the A2C model. It was held online, with the members of the Regional Stakeholder Panel, in November 2024, as a continuation of the third workshop and consisted of the validation and prioritisation of a range of statements, related with policy measures to promote the CE in the agrofood sector.

Contratación pública verde propuestas más prioritarias

1. **Plataforma de monitoreo público.**
2. **Certificación de Proveedor Circular, otorgando ventajas en los procesos de licitación pública.**
3. **Capacitación en Contratación pública verde para el personal de la administración pública a cargo de los procesos de licitación.**

5. The fifth workshop was held online on 17th January 2025, with the participation of the EU stakeholder panel. The aim of this workshop was to validate the A2C model and the self-assessment tool, evaluating their applicability to a wide range of EU regions and contexts (Figure 51). The results of this workshop are described in detail in the deliverables D7.16 Report on potential for adoption and scale up (M42).

6.2.5 Empower [updated]

ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION – SCALABILITY

Most preferred:

#1 - Create permanent working and coordination groups for by-products, with a regional register to facilitate reuse and recycling efforts.

#2 - Promote product lifetime extension through design for longevity and maintenance of durable goods, reducing waste generation.

Figure 51. Screenshot of the 5th online workshop for validation of A2C model

The activities of A2C have not covered specifically the empower level, as it was considered that this degree of engagement has been reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes implemented in the project, for instance, co-creating and validating the model and self-assessment tool, or elaborating policy recommendations . Hence, it is considered that the empower level has been reached indirectly, promoting 3 conditions among the public:

- An enhanced awareness about the CE, the territory and the sectors involved.
- The deployment of capacity building mechanisms at the individual and collective level.
- The generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation.

7 Evaluation of the results

The activities developed under the engagement strategy and their results have been analysed, and lessons have been extracted for the elaboration of the deliverable D7.11 A2C CE Action Plan elaborated by AGRO. Specifically, the lessons extracted from the Community based scheme carried out in Alhama de Murcia, together from the analysis of best practices in other regions, have been included in D7.4 by PRIMA.

The replicability and transferability of the public engagement activities within the region of Murcia is reflected in several deliverables, mainly the A2C Multidimensional Model and Self-Assessment tool (D7.10). Moreover, the CE Action Plan (CEAP) for the region of Murcia (D7.11) addresses the needs and barriers that hinder the development of CE in the agrofood industry and drafts actions that can be implemented to overcome them along action pillars: improvement of critical mass; development of human capital, training and education; improvement of governance models and access to funding schemes; and enhancement of standardisation and regulations. The document also proposes the stakeholders that may play a key role in implementing the proposed measures and hence, the document can be considered as a “public engagement strategy” at the long term, after the project completion.

- At the informative level, more than 20.000 people were reached by activities at the inform level. These indicators will be further detailed in the Dissemination and Communication Report-Final (D8.3).
- At the consult level, the participation in surveys and questionnaires benefitted in the campaigns offering direct benefits such as small gifts or participation in raffles. All in all, more than 100 people provided their feedback, showing a degree of awareness on the problem of food waste and plastic pollution, and a certain acceptance of upcycled products (lower in the case of food products). In the case of the interviews, they counted with the participation of more than 20 stakeholders among public administrations, civil society organisations, and teachers participating in the social impact assessment.
- At the involved level, the participation of vendors in the community-based scheme was lower than expected, but this was also related to the specificity of the fruit and vegetables to be used in A2C. There is a need for collaboration among different levels of public administrations (local, regional) to ensure consistent policies and measures.
- At the collaboration level, 5 co-creation workshops were held, each one with the participation of at least 5 out of 8 members of the Stakeholder Panels, representing Public

administrations, industry, research and civil society. Moreover, other collaborative activities have been performed with the other projects granted in the topic, such as co-organisation of workshops, participation in Events, further reported in D8.5.

8 Conclusions

The results obtained by the Public Engagement strategy could be applied at regional level through Action Plans, and at the European level in the D7.16 *Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential* of the A2C project and other EU regions, and the Action Plans to be developed for the replication in Lombardy (D7.17) and Lithuania (D7.18).

It must be highlighted that difficulties have been found along the project, to gather all the involved sectors and actors in the public engagement activities. These difficulties were different, depending on the level of engagement aimed:

- At the informative level, no significant barriers were found. The creation of the Spanish section of the website has served to overcome language hurdles and emailing campaigns. Talks, seminars and participation in third parties' events have been organized among the relevant stakeholders with the collaboration of CETEC, CETBIO, AGRO, PRIMA, KVC. The implementation of gamification techniques during the talks at primary and secondary school, such as Kahoot tests, was revealed as the most effective to engage the students.
- At the consult level, the barriers found were related to creating forms that were accessible (in terms of language and use of technologies) with the target groups. These hurdles were overcome with designing tailored forms with adapted language, the duplication of surveys (using ICT and printed surveys to avoid the digital gap), and the organization of deeper interviews that allow reformulating the questions and solving doubts as required during the process. In the case of citizens and local communities, the provision of small gifts (samples of products obtained during the project, the award at the market) solved the potential hurdle of low participation.
- At the involve level, the key role of public administrations and services at the regional and local level should be highlighted, providing participation infrastructures and facilitating the contact with relevant stakeholders, due to the long-time relationship and trust built before the project; nevertheless, this collaboration may be disrupted in case of political changes during the project lifecycle. To avoid this risk, collaboration was established with civil servants instead of policy makers, through meetings at the Local Development Agency and online, and allowed the direct contact with the market vendors, required for the community-based scheme in T7.1.2, as well as the social impact assessment. On the other hand, the engagement of representatives of public administrations at the collaboration level (regional stakeholder panel) granted that their advice and recommendations were incorporated in the A2C model.

- At the collaboration level, where higher commitment and time allocation is needed, there was a need to slightly change the composition of the Stakeholder Panels to maintain a balanced composition. This is aligned with the challenges reflected in the Diagnosis section for the collaboration level, due to the costly and time-consuming nature of the related activities. This problem was solved through the partners' collaboration, that suggested contacts in their networks, and the implementation of additional mailing campaigns.

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